

STUDIES IN THE NEGATIVELY CHARGED COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF VARIOUS FERRIC SALTS. PART. V. NEGATIVELY CHARGED FERRIC ARSENATE SOL

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This paper presents an investigation on the preparation and properties of the negatively charged colloidal solutions of ferric arsenate. The sols were prepared by dispersing freshly precipitated ferric arsenate by caustic soda in presence of glucose or glycerine. The composition of the sol peptised in presence of glucose is $11\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{FeAsO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and that of the sol peptised in presence of glycerine is $9\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{FeAsO}_4 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Various other characteristics of the sols have also been investigated.

Grimaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1884, 98, 1540) obtained the positively charged sol of ferric arsenate by the dialysis of a mixture of ferric chloride in excess and potassium arsenate. Holmes and Arnold (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 1014) showed that freshly precipitated ferric arsenate could also be peptised by ferric sulphate and ferric nitrate. Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587) studied various aspects of the formation of ferric arsenate jelly and Prakash and Dube (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 208, 163) studied the kinetics of the sol-gel transformation of this jelly. As no attempt appears to have been made to prepare and to study the negatively charged colloidal solution of ferric arsenate, this investigation was taken up in this laboratory. In this paper the experimental results on the compositions and various properties of such negatively charged sols of ferric arsenate have been reported. An idea of the peptisation of ferric arsenate by caustic soda in presence of glucose or glycerine can be had from the following figures.

1.0-2.0 C. c. of ferric chloride solution (30.36 g. of ferric oxide per litre), when mixed with 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of 20% potassium dihydrogen arsenate solution in presence of 0.1 to 3.0 c. c. of 20% glucose solution, requires 2.8 to 5.0 c. c. of 0.5N-NaOH solution (total volume 10 c. c.) to bring about complete peptisation in half an hour.

1.0-2.0 C. c. of the ferric chloride solution, when mixed with 1.0 to 3.0 c. c. of the potassium dihydrogen arsenate solution in presence of 1.0 to 3.0 c. c. of glycerine, requires 2.6 to 5.0 c. c. of 0.5N-NaOH solution (total volume 10 c. c.) to bring about complete peptisation in half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sol A was prepared by mixing 40 c. c. of ferric chloride solution (30.36 g. of ferric oxide per litre), 40 c. c. of 20% potassium dihydrogen arsenate solution, 20 c. c. of 20% glucose solution and 100 c. c. of 0.5N-NaOH solution. The total volume was kept at 200 c. c. The sol was dialysed for 15 days.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 40 c. c. of the same FeCl_3 solution, KH_2AsO_4 solution (40 c. c.), glycerine (20 c. c.) and 0.5N-NaOH solution (100 c. c.). The total volume was kept at 200 c. c. and the sol was dialysed for 15 days.

Composition of the Sols

The amount of iron in a known volume of the sol was estimated by the use of the reagent cupferron (Mushran and Prakash, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 413). The total arsenate was estimated as As_2S_3 (Bunsen's method). In order to ascertain the amount of the arsenate in combined state with iron, a known volume of the sol was coagulated by potassium chloride, the total coagulum was collected, washed and estimated as As_2S_3 . The coagula were also obtained cataphoretically and estimated for arsenate; the concordance of the results showed that the equilibrium between the free and the combined arsenate was not appreciably altered during these processes. The combined iron corresponding to this amount of arsenate was calculated on the assumption that the ferric arsenate was $FeAsO_4$. The rest of the iron was present as hydrated ferric oxide. From the ratio of the free to the combined iron, the empirical formula of the sol was calculated. The viscosity of the sol was measured by the Ostwald's method at 30° and the amount of bound water was calculated from the Hatschek's equation (vide Part I of this series, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 111).

TABLE I

Per litre.	Sol A	Sol B	Per litre.	Sol A	Sol B
	Glucose sol.	Glycerine sol.		Glucose sol.	Glycerine sol.
Total iron	0.9604 g.	0.9092 g.	Free iron	0.9804 g	0.8198 g.
Total arsenate (As)	0.2132	0.2306	Viscosity of sol	0.00840	0.00834
Combined arsenate (As)	0.1073	0.1200	Viscosity of water	0.00803	0.00608
Free arsenate (As)	0.1059	0.1106	Bound water	0.0854	0.0614
Combined iron	0.0800	0.0894	Empirical formula	$11Fe_2O_3 \cdot 2FeAsO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$.	$9Fe_2O_3 \cdot 2FeAsO_4 \cdot 3.6H_2O$.

The sols were coagulated cataphoretically as well as by 0.5N-KCl, centrifuged and the hydrogen-ion concentrations of the supernatant aqueous layers were determined by the Hildebrand's hydrogen electrode. The following pH values were recorded.

	Glucose sol (A).	Glycerine sol (B).
pH	7.04 (KCl coagulated)	7.03 (KCl coagulated)
	7.05 (cataphoretically coagulated)	7.06 (cataphoretically coagulated)

Conductivities of the Sols

In Table II are recorded the conductivities of these sols as affected by (a) dilution, (b) ageing, and (c) temperature.

TABLE IIa

Conductivity values at dilutions (30°).

Dilutions.	Conductivity of		Dilutions.	Conductivity of	
	sol A.	sol B		sol A.	sol B.
Original sol (X)	1.10×10^{-4} mho	2.06×10^{-4} mho	X/2	0.60×10^{-4} mho	1.05×10^{-4} mho
5X/6	0.96	1.73	X/3	0.40	0.72
2X/3	0.76	1.40	X/6	0.23	0.40

TABLE IIb

Conductivity values on ageing (30°).

Date.	Conductivity of		Date.	Conductivity of	
	sol A.	sol B.		sol A.	sol B.
25.11.45	1.10×10^{-4} mho	2.06×10^{-4} mho	26.4.46	1.22×10^{-4} mho	2.14×10^{-4} mho
20.12.45	1.14	2.08	10.5.46	1.24	2.16
20. 2.46	1.19	2.1	19.7.46	1.26	2.17

TABLE IIc

Conductivity values at diff. temps.

Temp.	Glucose sol (A).		Glycerine sol (B).	
	Conducty.	Diff. per 5°.	Conducty.	Diff. per 5°.
47°	1.30×10^{-4} mho		2.35×10^{-4} mho	
35°	1.20	0.10	2.18	0.17
30°	1.10	0.10	2.00	0.18
25°	0.99	0.11	1.82	0.18
20°	0.89	0.10	1.63	0.19
15°	0.80	0.09	1.45	0.18
Temp. of zero conductance (extrapolated)		-20.25°		-20.60°
Temp. coefficient per 1°	...	0.020		0.036

The above data indicate that the sols are pretty stable on dilution, as the conductivities of the sols are very nearly proportional to the dilutions. The conductivities of the sols increase with age. The conductivity-temperature curves are straight lines. The temperature of zero conductance of the sols range between -20.25° and -20.60° .

It will be of interest to study the temperature coefficients of the sols. The temperature coefficients per 1° along with the conductivities at 35° are given below.

	Conductivity at 35° .	Temp. coeff. per 1° .
Sol A	1.20×10^{-4} mho	0.020
Sol B	2.18	0.036

The temperature coefficient of sol A is thus 1.66% of the conductance at 35° and that of sol B is 1.65% of the conductance at 35° .

Extinction Coefficients of the Sols

Extinction coefficients of the sols were determined by the Nutting's spectrophotometer, at different dilutions and at different wave-lengths and the results are recorded in Table III (X stands for the original undiluted sol).

TABLE III

Wave-lengths.	Sol A. Dilutions.				Sol B. Dilutions.			
	X.	X/2.	X/4.	X/8.	X.	X/2.	X/4.	X/8.
4800 $\bar{\text{A}}$	2.40	1.21	0.61	0.31	1.33	0.67	0.34	0.17
4900	1.87	1.00	0.51	0.25	1.10	0.56	0.29	0.15
5000	1.60	0.81	0.41	0.20	0.98	0.50	0.26	0.13
5200	1.10	0.56	0.29	0.14	0.82	0.32	0.16	0.08
5400	0.78	0.38	0.20	0.10	0.45	0.23	0.12	0.06
5600	0.44	0.23	0.12	0.06	0.30	0.16	0.09	0.05
5800	0.33	0.17	0.09	0.05	0.21	0.11	0.06	0.03
6000	0.22	0.12	0.06	0.03	0.15	0.08	0.04	0.02

The above results show that the sols rigidly obey Beer's law i.e., the extinction coefficients are almost proportional to the dilutions. This suggests that the sols are quite stable and do not hydrolyse during the process of dilution. Our results on the conductivities of the sols at different dilutions (Table II Δ) also show similar behaviour.

Coagulation of the Sols

In Table IV are recorded the minimum amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate 1 c. c. of the sols in a total volume of 10 c. c., the time allowed in each case being 30 minutes.

TABLE IV

Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate		Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate	
	sol A.	sol B.		sol A.	sol B.
0.5 N-NaCl	0.50 c. c.	1.70	0.004 N-Ba (NO ₃) ₂	0.89 c. c.	1.10 c. c.
0.5 N-KCl	0.30	0.90	0.004 N-Sr (NO ₃) ₂	0.70	1.30
0.5 N-KNO ₃	0.30	0.90	0.004 N-AlCl ₃	0.30	0.40
0.5 N-KBr	0.30	0.90			

The coagulating powers of the ions thus fall in the following series :

The effect of dilution on the coagulation values has also been investigated and the results are recorded in Table V (total volume was 10 c. c.).

TABLE V

Electrolytes.	Amount necessary to coagulate (c. c.)					
	glucose sol (A)			glycerine sol (B)		
	1 c. c.	2 c. c.	3 c. c.	1 c. c.	2 c. c.	3 c. c.
0.5 N-NaCl	0.50	0.80	0.70	1.20	1.30	1.40
0.5 N-KCl	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.90	1.00	1.10
0.5 N-KNO ₃	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.90	1.00	1.10

From this table it is evident that the sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes and that they show the normal behaviour with dilution.

Positively Charged Ferric Arsenate Sols

In Table VI are recorded the compositions of some positively charged sols that we have prepared.

Sol A was prepared by dialysing a mixture of 40 c. c. of ferric chloride solution (69.84 g. of Fe₂O₃ per litre) and 15 c. c. of 20% potassium dihydrogen arsenate solution for 3 days.

Sol B was prepared by dialysing a mixture of 40 c. c. of ferric chloride solution (of the same strength) and 25 c. c. of 20% potassium dihydrogen arsenate solution for 4 days.

TABLE VI

Per litre.	Sol A.	Sol B.
Total iron	11.6476 g.	17.4151 g.
Combined arsenate (As)	7.1320	13.6583
Combined iron	6.3128	10.3234
Free iron	6.6850	7.0917
Viscosity of sol (30°)	0.00900	0.00928
Bound water	1.2520	2.4440
Empirical formula	3Fe ₂ O ₃ .5FeAsO ₄ .4H ₂ O.	Fe ₂ O ₃ .3FeAsO ₄ .3H ₂ O.
Chloride ions per litre	3.4220 g.	3.3190 g.

DISCUSSION

According to Pfaff (*Akad. Handl. Stockholm*, 1818, 22, 255) a solution of ferric chloride gives a white precipitate when treated with disodium hydrogen arsenate. Various investigators have analysed this precipitate. The analysis given by Berzelius (*ibid.*, 1824, 28, 354) corresponds to ferric monohydrogen arsenate, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{HAsO}_4) \cdot 4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Metzke (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1910, 32, 626) obtained ferric dihydrogen arsenate, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{AsO}_4) \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, by dissolving artificial pharmacosiderite in syrupy arsenic acid and heating this solution. Usually when a dipotassium arsenate solution is added to an excess of ferric chloride, the substance precipitated is monohydrogen arsenate according to the following equation :

When the precipitation is carried out by potassium dihydrogen arsenate, the precipitate obtained is very likely ferric dihydrogen arsenate :

This is the expected composition of the positively charged ferric arsenate sol obtained by peptising the ferric dihydrogen arsenate with ferric chloride. But in the case of negatively charged sols, which are prepared in presence of excess of alkali, the constitution probably corresponds to ferric *ortho*arsenate, FeAsO_4 :

In the course of dialysis, most of the sodium arsenate, thus formed, is eliminated, but the sol still contains a considerable amount of ferric arsenate. A portion of ferric arsenate is also hydrolysed during the course of dialysis and the following equilibria are ultimately maintained :

The compositions of the negatively and positively charged ferric arsenate sols are given below. For comparison, positively charged ferric arsenate sols have also been expressed in terms of FeAsO_4 (though it is very likely that the actual composition corresponds to dihydrogen arsenate).

Negatively charged :

Positively charged :

It is thus clear that the positively charged ferric arsenate sols contain a larger content of arsenate combined with iron than the negatively charged sols.

We have studied in details the various characteristics of the negatively charged sols and from the results recorded in the foregoing tables, the following observations may be summarised :

1. The electrical conductivities of the sols are proportionate to the dilutions.
2. The electrical conductivities of the sols are linear functions of temperatures of zero conductance. Temperature of zero conductance lies between -20.25° and -20.60° .
3. The temperature coefficients of conductivity per 1° of the sols are always less than 2% of the conductances at 35° .
4. With ageing, the conductivities of the sols increase.
5. Measurements of extinction coefficients show that the sols obey Beer's law.
6. The pH values of the dispersion medium lie between 7.02 and 7.06 showing that the sols are slightly basic owing to the stabilising hydroxide ions.
7. The sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution.

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